

Association between Service Quality & Customer Satisfaction: Theoretical Perspective in Tourism Industry

Authors Name: ¹Dr. Goldi Puri ²Kuldeep Singh

Affiliations: ¹Associate Professor, Institute of Hotel and Tourism Management, Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak, Haryana

²Research Scholar, Institute of Hotel and Tourism Management, Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak, Haryana

Abstract

Tourist behavior has become more multifaceted and difficult regarding the selection of tourist attraction and services. The main focus of this paper is to understand the relationship of service quality and customer satisfaction in tourism industry. From the previous studies, it was established that there is a positive association amid customer satisfaction and service quality which attracts tourists to visit the destinations. This paper discussed the dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction from the previous researchers' viewpoint. In addition, authors also discussed the importance of SERVQUAL Model and highlight its criticism also. The paper is based majorly on secondary data collected from different published research articles, book chapters, reports etc. This paper also discussed the future implication with some management strategies to improve service quality for tourists.

Keywords: *Services, Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, Tourists, SERVQUAL*

Introduction

There is a widespread exposure in the study of satisfaction among tourists and service quality in any tourist attraction (Andreassen, 1994; Burns et al., 2003). It is to be noted that there are many conceptual and theoretical debates on the subject of the resemblances and dissimilarities amid satisfaction and levels of quality. According to Oliver (1981) and Parasuraman et al. (1994) the most significant distinction is that the outlook applied to depict service quality and satisfaction are dissimilar in nature. Further, Storbacka et al. (1994) also found the association among the notions of service quality and satisfaction by means of a table with four groupings. In their study, price is the reason of distinctions. In addition, Tian-Cole & Crompton (2003) assume that the perceived quality is directly correlated to consumer satisfaction in tourist attractions and also satisfaction is associated to loyalty towards the destinations while making choices in selecting a destination.

According to Berry (1980), services are described as performances, activities or actions. In contrast, goods can be characterized as objects, resources, or belongings (pp. 24-29).

Definitions of Service Quality

Service quality has been defined as a “distinction amid the consumer’s expectations of a service and the consumer’s perceptions of the service received” (**Parasuraman et al., 1985**).

Grönroos (1984) described service quality as “the result of an assessment procedure while purchaser evaluates his expectations through the service he has actually delivered from the suppliers.

Bitner and Hubbert (1994) labeled service quality as “the buyer’s general intuition of the comparative inadequacy and supremacy of the service providers (p. 77).

Definitions of Customer Satisfaction

Hu et al. (2009) described consumer satisfaction as “an emotional response that appears in reaction to a particular and extended set of services” (p. 115).

Kondou (1999) in his study described customer satisfaction as an optimistic expressive reaction resultant from consumers’ prejudiced appraisals of their understanding.

Bitner and Hubbert (1994) noted satisfaction of consumers as a “meaning of pleasure with numerous service deliveries and understandings with the organization”.

Importance of Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

In service sector consumer buying activities is multifaceted and an evenly composite network of varied decisions. Service providers are concerned in expressive equally, the diverse mechanism of consumer activities and the aspects that contains noteworthy controls on these activities. Promotion strategy has strived to build up into the procedure of buying activities and diverse representations have been claimed to elucidate it. The mechanisms of these models are acknowledgment of need, information seek out, assessment of substitutes, purchase and spending and post purchase assessment.

From the scholars standpoint, service quality also entrenched in service escape procedure is consequently tough for participants to reproduction and business can achieve a viable benefit through improved service quality. In addition, services are also mechanism of promotion in state of goods industrialized production. When manufactured goods start on to vanish, service quality presumes value for goods also.

Review of Literature

In service sector, attributes of perceived service quality and consumer satisfaction have conventionally measured. According to Howat et al. (1996) satisfaction is appraised by utilizing items relied on the 5 proportions of perceived service quality advocated by Parasuraman et al. (1988). From the “expectancy-disconfirmation paradigm” that shaped the root of the SERVQUAL model, service quality was described as the “*gap amid expectation and perception*” (Parasuraman et al., 1988). In contrast consumer satisfaction was recognized when expectations can be matching with the actual service or ahead of these prospects” (Oliver, 1980).

Although researchers now commonly agree on the subject of the uniqueness and descriptions of perceived service quality and satisfaction, the fundamental association is still not clear. Researchers like (Bitner, 1990; Bolton and Drew, 1991) have recommended that “satisfaction of consumers is a precursor of perceived service quality”. They argued that satisfaction arbitrates a position of coherent credits concerning the prospects of customer’s services and their assessment.

Relationship between Service Quality & Customer Satisfaction

In his study, Oliver (1981) stated that “tourist satisfaction can be analyzed after purchasing tourism products”. In several literatures, satisfaction is explained as a precursor of trustworthiness (Kozak, 2001; Jang & Feng, 2006).

Seetanah et al. (2020) analyzed the satisfaction of tourist and their relationship with service quality of airport at destinations and revisit intention. An empirical study was conducted and effect of tourist satisfaction with destination on behavioral intention was studied. Meng and Cui (2020) found that there are some important constructs for the creation of revisit intentions in home accommodations. Manan et al. (2019) found that precursor of “customer satisfaction” like “atmosphere” “food quality” “service quality” “perceived value” and “other consumers” had significant influence on “customer satisfaction” in Bangladesh tourism industry.

Chi and Qu (2008) declared that “satisfaction among consumers has constantly been judged as a crucial aspiration in service sector because it was implied that pleased consumer would purchase more as compared to unsatisfied consumer”. Likewise, Baker & Crompton (2000) and Jang & Feng (2006) argued that “satisfaction is the principal precursor of intention to revisit”. Prominently, an argument is still amid numerous researchers that satisfaction provides a view for high publicity of products and recommendations of destinations which can augment satisfaction (Kozak & Rimmington, 2000; Yoon & Uysal 2005; Chi & Qu, 2008).

SERVQUAL Scale

It is to be noted that the establishment for the SERVQUAL scale is the gap model anticipated by Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988). Within the concept of disconfirmation paradigm, the gap model sustains that consumer satisfaction is correlated to the dimension and aspects of disconfirmation of an individual's familiarity (Smith and Houston, 1982; Churchill and Surprenant, 1982; Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, 1985). In addition, Parasuraman et al. (1988) argued that "dissatisfaction occurs in consumer's mind *when final services are smaller than predictable services*. In contrast, "*if apparent services are greater than anticipated service it creates satisfaction in the mind of consumers*."

SERVPERF Scale

Cronin and Taylor (1992) were the initial scholars who criticized utmost the concept of SERVQUAL instrument. They raised the question on speculative source of the SERVQUAL scale and initiate it mystifying with consumer satisfaction. For that reason, they claimed that prospects elements of SERVQUAL can be superfluous and in its place performance element can only applied. They anticipated the new instrument known as the 'SERVPERF' scale.

Research Methodology

This research is a based on majorly secondary data collected from different published research articles, book chapters, government policies, reports, tourism policies and websites . In addition, this paper carries out the effect of discussion with tourist, service providers and officials.

Determinants of service quality

Many scholars like Sasser et al. (1978), Berry et al. (1985) & Johnston and Lyth (1991) argued that expectations of customers are multidimensional in nature and not focus on the only single aspect. According to Parasuraman et al. (1985) there are ten factors of service quality which are courtesy, communication, access, competence, reliability, credibility, security, responsiveness, tangible and understanding. Berry et al. (1985) investigated the relationship among security, credibility, competence, courtesy and communication and between understanding and access. After that they applied the five main aspects of service quality which are empathy, assurance, reliability, responsiveness and tangible. They measured the service quality with the help of these five dimensions and used SERVQUAL scale of (Parasuraman et al., 1988; Zeithaml et al., 1990).

Criticism of SERVQUAL

There is also a criticism from many researchers on using the SERVQUAL model and various studies challenged the disparity between expectations and perceptions. According to Carman

(1990) and Babakus and Boller (1992) there should be usage of only perception scores and there is an impact of overall service quality and had stronger co relation. Further, Babakus and Boller (1992) emphasized that dimension of service quality is mainly relied on the kind of sector which is investigated and also the planning of a particular industry is more suitable as compared to the general one. Also, Parasuraman et al. (1988, 1991) discussed the wide area of strength and weakness in the delivery of service quality. Several researches which are related to quality of services are assessed by this model and bring attention to the mind of customers.

Conclusion and Future Implication

This paper highlights the affiliation amid customer satisfaction and service quality in tourism industry and explained the major review of tourism scholars. According to researchers service quality dimensions over customer satisfaction are positively correlated. If we take into account that tourists when choosing a tourist destination for their vacation it is vital from service provider to endow in service quality to improve the experience of tourists and enhances their satisfaction which can increase loyalty.

The insight of this study also facilitates destination managers and service providers to enhance the service quality in tourist destinations. This study can also contribute for the scholars in future to recognize the notions of service quality and customer satisfaction.

References

- Andreassen, T.W. (1994). Satisfaction, loyalty and reputation as indicators of customer orientation in the public sector. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 7(2), 16–34.
- Babakus, E and Boller, G W (1992). “An Empirical Assessment of the Servqual Scale,” *Journal of Business Research*, 24(3), 253-68.
- Baker, D. A. & Crompton, J. L. (2000). Quality, satisfaction and behavioural intentions. *Annals of tourism research*, 27(3), 785-804.
- Berry, L. L. (1980). Services marketing is different. *Business*, 30(3), 24-29.
- Berry, L.L., Zeithaml, V.A. and Parasuraman, A. (1985), “Quality counts in services, too”, *Business Horizons*, May-June, pp. 44-52.

Bitner, M.J. (1990), "Evaluating service encounters: the effects of physical surroundings and employee responses", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 54 No. 2, pp. 69-82.

Bitner, M. J., & Hubbert, A. R. (1994). Encounter satisfaction versus overall satisfaction versus quality: The customer's voice. In R. T. Rust & R. L. Oliver (Eds.), *Service quality, new directions in theory and practice* (pp. 79-94). London, UK: Sage.

Burns, R., Graefe, A.R., & Absher, J.D. (2003). Alternate measurement approaches to recreational customer satisfaction: Satisfaction only versus gap scores. *Leisure Sciences*, 25, 363–380.

Carman, J.M. (1990), "Consumer perceptions of service quality: an assessment of the SERVQUAL dimensions", *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 66 No. 1, pp. 33-55.

Chi, C. G. Q. & Qu, H. (2008). Examining the structural relationships of destination image, tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty: An integrated approach. *Tourism management*, 29(4), 624-636.

Churchill, G A and Surprenant, C (1982). "An Investigation into the Determinants of Customer Satisfaction," *Journal of Marketing Research*, 19(November), 491-504.

Cronin, J.J., & Taylor, S.A. (1992). Measuring service quality: A reexamination and extension. *Journal of Marketing*, 56(3), 55–69.

Grönroos, C. (1984). A service quality model and its marketing implications. *European Journal of Marketing*, 18(4), 36-44.

Howat, G., Absher, J., Crilley, G. and Milne, I. (1996), "Measuring customer service quality in sports and leisure center", *Managing Leisure*, Vol. 1, pp. 77-89.

Hu, H. H. S., Kandampully, J., & Juwaheer, T. D. (2009). Relationships and impacts of service quality, perceived value, customer satisfaction, and image: An empirical study. *The Service Industries Journal*, 29(2), 111-125.

Jang, S. & Feng, R. (2007). Temporal destination revisit intention: The effects of Novelty seeking and satisfaction. *Tourism Management*, 28, 580-590.

Johnston, R. and Lyth, D. (1991), "Service quality: implementing the integration of customer expectations and operational capability", in Brown, S.W., Gummesson, E., Edvardsson, B.

and Gustavsson, B. (Eds), *Service Quality: Multidisciplinary and Multinational Perspectives*, Lexington Books, Lexington, MA.

Kondou, T. (1999). *Service marketing*. Tokyo, Japan: Society Economic Publication.

Kozak, M. (2001). Repeaters' behaviour at two distinct destinations. *Annals of tourism research*, 28(3), 784-807.

Kozak, M. & Rimmington, M. (2000). Tourist satisfaction with Mallorca, Spain, as an Offseason holiday destination. *Journal of Travel Research*, 38, 260-269.

Mannan, M., Chowdhury, N., Sarker, P., & Amir, R. (2019). Modeling customer satisfaction and revisit intention in Bangladeshi dining restaurants. *Journal of Modelling in Management*.

Meng, B., & Cui, M. (2020). The role of co-creation experience in forming tourists' revisit intention to home-based accommodation: Extending the theory of planned behavior. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 33, 100581.

Oliver, R.L. (1980). A cognitive model of the antecedents and consequences of satisfaction decisions. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 17, 460–469.

Oliver, R. (1981). Measurement and evaluation of satisfaction process in retail settings. *Journal of Retailing*, 57, 25–48.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A., & Berry, L.L. (1985). A conceptual model of service quality and its implications for future research. *Journal of Marketing*, 49(4), 41–50.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A. and Berry, L.L. (1988), “SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality”, *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 64 No. 1, pp. 12-40.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A. and Berry, L.L. (1991), “Refinement and reassessment of the SERVQUAL scale”, *Journal of Retailing*, Vol. 67 No. 4, pp. 42-50.

Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V.A., & Berry, L.L. (1994). Reassessment of expectations as a comparison standard in measuring service quality: Implications for further research. *Journal of Marketing*, 58(1), 111–124.

Seetana, B., Teeroovengadam, V., & Nunkoo, R. (2020). Destination satisfaction and revisit intention of tourists: does the quality of airport services matter? *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 44(1), 134-148.

Smith, R A and Houston, M J (1982). "Script-based Evaluations of Satisfaction with Services," in Berry, L, Shostack, G and Upah, G (eds.), *Emerging Perspectives on Services Marketing*, Chicago: American Marketing Association, 59-62.

Tian-Cole, S., & Crompton, J.L. (2003). A conceptualization of the relationships between service quality and visitor satisfaction, and their links to destination selection. *Leisure Studies*, 22, 65–80.

Yoon, Y. & Uysal, M. (2005). An examination of the effects of motivation and satisfaction on destination loyalty: a structural model. *Tourism Management*, 26(1), 45-56.

Zeithaml, V.A., Parasuraman, A. and Berry, L.L. (1990), *Delivering Service Quality*, Free Press, New York, NY.